

A Unified Framework for Quantum Measurement: Time as Fields of Experience and Potential

Payman Sattari

Independent Researcher

psattari@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

We propose a new theoretical framework that reconceptualizes time and quantum measurement through the interaction of two fundamental fields: a field of experience and a field of potential. Rather than treating quantum measurement as random collapse of probability waves, we suggest that measurement represents the structured conversion of potential states into experiential ones. This framework naturally resolves several persistent puzzles in quantum mechanics, including the measurement problem, the role of consciousness in measurement, and the quantum-to-classical transition. We present specific, testable predictions that distinguish our framework from standard quantum mechanics, including: systematic correlations between sequential measurements, observable differences between systems with identical current states but different measurement histories, and specific patterns in how probability distributions evolve based on measurement timing and observer conditions. While developed through metaphysical investigation, this framework offers concrete implications for physics that invite experimental testing and mathematical formalization.

KEYWORDS: quantum measurement, consciousness, field theory, time, quantum-classical transition, experiential fields, potential fields

I. INTRODUCTION

The quantum measurement problem remains one of physics' most persistent puzzles [30, 31]. Despite quantum mechanics' extraordinary predictive success, we still lack a satisfying explanation for several fundamental issues: why measurement appears to "collapse" quantum systems into specific states, why these states follow probabilistic rather than deterministic rules, and most puzzlingly, why consciousness seems to play a special role in this process [32]. While various interpretations of quantum mechanics describe these phenomena mathematically, none fully explains the underlying mechanism or resolves the deeper questions about the nature of measurement, time, and observation.

Previous attempts to address these issues have ranged from the Copenhagen interpretation's pragmatic approach [6, 19] to more recent theories involving quantum

43 decoherence [33], many-worlds interpretations [12], and consciousness-based collapse models
44 [29, 32]. While each offers valuable insights, none has provided a unified explanation for the
45 measurement process, the role of consciousness, and the quantum-to-classical transition [23].

46 Current approaches typically treat measurement either as a fundamental, irreducible
47 feature of quantum mechanics or attempt to explain it through decoherence theory. However,
48 neither approach addresses why specific measurements yield specific outcomes, or why
49 measurement history appears to influence future probability distributions in ways our current
50 models don't fully capture. More fundamentally, these approaches don't explain why time itself
51 appears to behave differently at the quantum level, where multiple potential futures seem to
52 exist simultaneously until measurement occurs.

53 This paper presents a novel theoretical framework developed through sustained
54 investigation into the relationship between consciousness and physical reality. Rather than
55 beginning from conventional physical assumptions, we propose reconceptualizing both
56 measurement and time itself. In this framework, reality emerges through the interaction of two
57 fundamental fields: a field of experience (traditionally considered "the past") and a field of
58 potential (traditionally considered "the future"). Quantum measurement isn't a mysterious
59 collapse of probability waves but a natural conversion of potential states into experiential states
60 through the act of observation.

61 This framework makes several specific, testable predictions about quantum
62 measurement outcomes that differ from current theory. These include systematic correlations
63 between sequential measurements that reflect the building of experiential fields, observable
64 differences between systems with identical current states but different measurement histories,
65 and specific patterns in how probability distributions evolve based on measurement timing and
66 observer conditions.

67 While developed through metaphysical investigation rather than conventional physical
68 theory, this framework offers concrete predictions that can be tested experimentally. It suggests
69 new ways of understanding quantum phenomena that resolve long-standing paradoxes while
70 maintaining scientific rigor. Most importantly, it provides a natural explanation for why
71 consciousness appears necessary for measurement while avoiding both the extremes of pure
72 materialism and quantum mysticism.

73

74

75

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

76

A. RECONCEPTUALIZING TIME

78

79 Traditional physics treats time as a linear progression [26, 27], with quantum mechanics
80 suggesting multiple potential futures that collapse into a single reality upon measurement. We
81 propose instead that what we call "time" is better understood as the interaction between two
82 fundamental fields: a field of experience and a field of potential. These aren't abstract
83 mathematical constructs but real, interacting aspects of nature that explain both quantum
84 behavior and our experience of time's flow.

85 The field of experience represents actualized states - not merely "past events" but a
 86 living field of energy that exists Now and influences probability distributions in quantum systems.
 87 Similarly, the field of potential represents not just possible futures but a real field of unrealized
 88 states that exist simultaneously until actualized through measurement. This differs
 89 fundamentally from the conventional view of quantum superposition, suggesting instead that
 90 potential states are as real as actualized ones, just existing in a different field.

91 The constant Now, rather than being a moving point on a timeline, represents the
 92 interface where consciousness converts states from the field of potential into the field of
 93 experience. This conversion isn't random but is influenced by the existing field of experience,
 94 explaining both the probabilistic nature of quantum mechanics and why measurement histories
 95 affect future outcomes.

97 B. IMPLICATIONS FOR QUANTUM MEASUREMENT

98
 99 This framework suggests that quantum measurement outcomes aren't purely random but are
 100 influenced by the accumulated field of experience in systematic ways. This influence manifests
 101 through several key mechanisms:

- 102
 103 1. **Field Memory:** Each measurement contributes to an accumulating experiential field that
 104 subtly influences future measurements. Unlike standard quantum mechanics where
 105 each measurement is treated as independent, our framework predicts subtle correlations
 106 between sequential measurements based on the system's measurement history.
- 107 2. **Temporal Relationships:** The influence of past measurements doesn't simply decay
 108 linearly with time but shows complex patterns reflecting the interaction between
 109 experiential and potential fields. These patterns should manifest as resonance-like
 110 effects where certain temporal spacings between measurements show enhanced
 111 correlations.
- 112 3. **Observer-System Coupling:** The state of the measuring consciousness affects how
 113 potential states convert to experiential ones, leading to systematic variations in
 114 measurement outcomes while maintaining overall quantum statistics. This explains why
 115 different observers might see slightly different probability distributions while still
 116 preserving quantum mechanical consistency.
- 117 4. **Scale-Dependent Effects:** As systems become larger and more complex, they
 118 accumulate more extensive experiential fields. This naturally explains the emergence of
 119 classical behavior in macroscopic systems while preserving quantum effects at
 120 microscopic scales.

122 C. BRIDGING QUANTUM AND CLASSICAL BEHAVIOR

123
 124 Our framework provides a natural explanation for the quantum-to-classical transition. Rather
 125 than treating this transition as mysterious or merely a result of decoherence [20, 28], we
 126 suggest it emerges naturally from the accumulation of experiential fields as systems grow in
 127 size and complexity. This explains:
 128

- 129 ● Why quantum effects become less prominent at larger scales
- 130 ● How classical determinism emerges from quantum probability
- 131 ● Why measurement appears necessary at quantum scales but not classical ones
- 132 ● How quantum and classical behaviors can coexist in the same system

133
134

135 III. PREDICTED PHENOMENA

136

137 Our framework makes several specific, testable predictions that distinguish it from standard
138 quantum mechanics. These predictions emerge naturally from treating quantum measurement
139 as an interaction between fields of experience and potential, mediated by consciousness [5, 16].

140

141 A. SEQUENTIAL MEASUREMENT EFFECTS

142

143 The most directly testable predictions involve sequential measurements on quantum systems:

144

- 145 1. **Memory Effects:** Our framework predicts that sequential measurements on identically
146 prepared quantum systems should show subtle but measurable correlations that depend
147 on:

- 148 a. The temporal spacing between measurements
- 149 b. The precision of previous measurements
- 150 c. The accumulated measurement history
- 151 d. The state of the measuring consciousness

152 Unlike standard quantum mechanics, which treats each measurement as independent,
153 we predict that measurement outcomes should show systematic patterns reflecting the
154 building of experiential fields.

- 155 2. **Temporal Resonances:** We predict specific temporal patterns in measurement
156 correlations:

- 157 a. Enhanced correlations at certain temporal spacings
- 158 b. Non-monotonic decay of measurement influences
- 159 c. Systematic variations based on measurement timing
- 160 d. Pattern formation in sequential measurements

161 These patterns should be distinguishable from random fluctuations or experimental
162 artifacts through their specific temporal signatures.

163

164 B. OBSERVER-DEPENDENT EFFECTS

165 Our framework makes unique predictions about how different observers affect quantum
166 systems:

167 1. Observer State Dependence

- 168 ● Different observers should show subtle but measurable variations in
169 measurement outcomes
- 170 ● These variations should follow systematic patterns based on observer conditions

- 171 • Multiple observers measuring the same system should show correlations
172 reflecting their relative states
173 • The precision and clarity of measurement should depend on observer focus and
174 attention

175 **2. Collective Observer Effects**

- 176 • Multiple observers measuring simultaneously should show different patterns than
177 sequential observations
178 • Observer coordination should affect measurement outcomes
179 • Group consciousness effects should be detectable in carefully controlled
180 conditions

181 **C. SCALE TRANSITION PREDICTIONS**

182 Our framework makes specific predictions about how quantum effects transition to classical
183 behavior:

184 **1. System Size Effects**

- 185 • Quantum effects should fade gradually and systematically with increasing system
186 size
187 • The transition should follow specific patterns based on system complexity
188 • Remnants of quantum behavior should be detectable even in larger systems
189 under specific conditions

190 **2. Complexity Dependence**

- 191 • More complex systems should show faster transition to classical behavior
192 • The transition should depend on both size and internal organization
193 • Systems with different internal coherence should show different transition
194 patterns

195 **D. EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOLS**

196 We propose several specific experimental configurations to test these predictions:

197 **1. Modified Double-Slit Experiment**

- 198 • Sequential measurements at precise temporal intervals
199 • Variation of observer conditions
200 • Multiple observer configurations
201 • Pattern analysis in interference distributions

202 **2. Quantum Oscillator Studies**

- 203 • Precise control of measurement timing
204 • Sequential measurement series
205 • Observer variation studies
206 • Temporal correlation analysis

207 **3. Scale Transition Studies**

- 208 • Systematic variation of system size
209 • Complexity variation experiments

- 245 ● Initial which-path detection
- 246 ● Intermediate position measurements
- 247 ● Final interference pattern
- 248 ● Temporal correlations between measurements
- 249 **2. Quantum Oscillator Studies Implementation Requirements:**
- 250 ● Trapped ion or similar quantum system
- 251 ● Precise state preparation
- 252 ● Multiple measurement capabilities
- 253 ● Observer condition monitoring

254 Measurement Series:

- 255 ● Sequential state measurements
- 256 ● Varying temporal intervals
- 257 ● Multiple observer configurations
- 258 ● Pattern correlation analysis

259 C. ADDRESSING POTENTIAL CHALLENGES

- 260 **1. Environmental Factors Critical Controls:**
- 261 ● Temperature stability
- 262 ● Electromagnetic shielding
- 263 ● Vibration isolation
- 264 ● Vacuum maintenance
- 265 ● Background radiation monitoring
- 266 **2. Observer-Related Considerations Essential Protocols:**
- 267 ● Clear observer state documentation
- 268 ● Standardized measurement procedures
- 269 ● Multiple observer coordination
- 270 ● Observer bias elimination
- 271 **3. Data Quality Assurance Key Requirements:**
- 272 ● High-precision timing records
- 273 ● Complete measurement histories
- 274 ● Environmental condition logs
- 275 ● Observer state documentation
- 276 ● System stability verification

277 D. STATISTICAL ANALYSIS FRAMEWORK

- 278 **1. Primary Analysis Methods**
- 279 ● Pattern recognition in measurement sequences
- 280 ● Temporal correlation analysis
- 281 ● Observer effect analysis
- 282 ● Scale transition analysis
- 283 **2. Validation Criteria:** For results to be considered significant:

- 284 ● Clear distinction from random fluctuations
- 285 ● Statistical significance beyond 5σ
- 286 ● Reproducibility across configurations
- 287 ● Independence from environmental artifacts
- 288 ● Consistency with theoretical predictions

289 E. PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATION STRATEGY

- 290 1. **Staged Approach:** We recommend implementing experiments in phases:
 - 291 ● Initial proof-of-concept studies
 - 292 ● Refined measurement protocols
 - 293 ● Multiple observer studies
 - 294 ● Scale transition investigations
- 295 2. **Quality Assurance:** Essential elements:
 - 296 ● Independent verification protocols
 - 297 ● Cross-laboratory validation
 - 298 ● Blind analysis procedures
 - 299 ● Rigorous peer review
- 300 3. **Documentation Requirements:** Comprehensive records of:
 - 301 ● All experimental parameters
 - 302 ● Environmental conditions
 - 303 ● Observer states and procedures
 - 304 ● Raw data and analysis methods

305

306

V. IMPLICATIONS

307 The framework we present suggests profound implications not just for quantum mechanics but
 308 for our fundamental understanding of reality. These implications span from specific physics
 309 problems to broader questions about consciousness and the nature of existence.

310 A. RESOLUTION OF FUNDAMENTAL PHYSICS PROBLEMS

- 311 1. **The Measurement Problem:** Our framework naturally resolves the quantum
 312 measurement problem [4] by:
 - 313 ● Explaining the mechanism of wave function "collapse" as conversion between
 314 fields
 - 315 ● Clarifying why specific measurements yield specific outcomes
 - 316 ● Showing why measurement appears probabilistic yet follows patterns
 - 317 ● Explaining the role of consciousness without mysticism
- 318 2. **The Observer Problem:** The framework resolves the long-standing puzzle of the
 319 observer by:
 - 320 ● Showing why consciousness is necessary for measurement
 - 321 ● Explaining how observation affects physical systems

- 322 ● Maintaining scientific objectivity while incorporating consciousness
- 323 ● Providing a testable model of observer-system interaction
- 324 3. **The Quantum-Classical Transition:** Our approach explains the emergence of classical
- 325 behavior through:
- 326 ● Natural accumulation of experiential fields
- 327 ● Scale-dependent transition mechanisms
- 328 ● Resolution of the micro-macro divide
- 329 ● Clear explanation of why different rules appear to apply at different scales

330 B. BROADER THEORETICAL IMPLICATIONS

- 331 1. **Nature of Time:** The framework suggests that:
 - 332 ● Time emerges from field interactions rather than existing as an absolute
 - 333 dimension
 - 334 ● The past exists as a field of experience rather than a fixed timeline
 - 335 ● The future exists as a field of potential rather than predetermined events
 - 336 ● The present represents the interface where potential becomes experience
- 337 2. **Consciousness and Reality:** Our framework indicates that:
 - 338 ● Consciousness is fundamental to reality's structure
 - 339 ● Subjective experience and objective physics are complementary aspects of the
 - 340 same process
 - 341 ● The inner/outer divide is bridged through field interactions
 - 342 ● Mind and matter interact through specific, measurable mechanisms
- 343 3. **Physical Law and Causality:** The framework suggests that:
 - 344 ● Physical laws emerge from patterns in field interactions
 - 345 ● Causality arises from the conversion of potential to experience
 - 346 ● Probability and determinism are complementary aspects of reality
 - 347 ● Natural law reflects the structure of consciousness-reality interaction

348 C. PRACTICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS

- 349 1. **Measurement Technology:** Potential applications include:
 - 350 ● New approaches to quantum measurement
 - 351 ● Enhanced precision through conscious interaction
 - 352 ● Novel quantum sensing technologies
 - 353 ● Improved quantum control methods
- 354 2. **Information Processing:** The framework suggests new possibilities for:
 - 355 ● Quantum computing architectures
 - 356 ● Information storage and retrieval
 - 357 ● Pattern recognition systems
 - 358 ● Consciousness-based computing
- 359 3. **Experimental Physics:** Implications for:
 - 360 ● Design of quantum experiments
 - 361 ● Understanding measurement limitations
 - 362 ● New experimental approaches

- 363 • Enhanced measurement precision

364 **D. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS**

- 365 1. **Theoretical Development:** Key areas for investigation:
- 366 • Mathematical formalization of field interactions
- 367 • Integration with quantum field theory
- 368 • Connection to theories of gravity
- 369 • Models of consciousness-matter interaction
- 370 2. **Experimental Programs:** Priority areas:
- 371 • Verification of predicted patterns
- 372 • Development of new measurement techniques
- 373 • Investigation of scale transitions
- 374 • Study of observer effects
- 375 3. **Technological Applications:** Potential developments:
- 376 • New measurement devices
- 377 • Enhanced quantum control systems
- 378 • Consciousness-based technologies
- 379 • Information processing applications

380

381

VI. CONCLUSION

382 The framework presented in this paper offers a novel approach to understanding quantum
 383 mechanics and measurement through the interaction of experiential and potential fields. While
 384 developed through metaphysical investigation rather than conventional physical theory, it
 385 provides specific, testable predictions that could resolve several fundamental problems in
 386 physics while suggesting new experimental directions.

387 The key strength of this framework lies in its natural resolution of long-standing
 388 paradoxes. The quantum measurement problem, the role of consciousness in observation, the
 389 quantum-to-classical transition, and the nature of time itself find coherent explanations within a
 390 single conceptual structure. Rather than treating these as separate puzzles requiring distinct
 391 solutions, our framework shows how they emerge from the same underlying principles.

392 Specifically, this framework:

- 393 • Explains quantum measurement as conversion between fields rather than mysterious
 394 collapse
- 395 • Shows why consciousness appears necessary for measurement while maintaining
 396 scientific objectivity
- 397 • Provides a natural explanation for the quantum-to-classical transition
- 398 • Suggests specific experimental protocols for testing its predictions

399 The experimental predictions we've outlined offer clear ways to test this framework
 400 against standard quantum mechanics. These aren't merely philosophical distinctions but
 401 measurable differences in how quantum systems should behave under specific conditions. The
 402 proposed experiments are feasible with current technology and would provide definitive
 403 evidence for or against our predictions.

404 While the mathematics of this framework remains to be fully developed, its conceptual
 405 coherence and explanatory power suggest it deserves serious consideration by the physics
 406 community. The framework's ability to resolve multiple foundational problems while generating
 407 new predictions indicates it may capture something fundamental about the nature of reality.

408 Looking forward, this work opens several crucial research directions:

- 409 1. Development of precise mathematical formalism through collaboration with theoretical
 410 physicists
- 411 2. Implementation of proposed experimental tests
- 412 3. Investigation of technological applications
- 413 4. Exploration of implications for our understanding of consciousness and reality

414 We acknowledge that proposing such a fundamental reconceptualization of physics requires
 415 extraordinary evidence. The framework presented here should be viewed as a starting point for
 416 investigation. However, its potential to resolve long-standing paradoxes while suggesting new
 417 experimental directions warrants serious consideration.

418 The history of physics shows that major advances often come from reconsidering basic
 419 assumptions about the nature of reality. If the predictions outlined here are confirmed
 420 experimentally, this framework could represent a significant step toward a deeper understanding
 421 of quantum mechanics, consciousness, and the fundamental nature of reality itself.

422 We invite the physics community to engage with these ideas, test the predictions, and
 423 help develop the mathematical formalism needed to fully express these concepts in physical
 424 theory. Whether our specific predictions are confirmed or not, we believe this approach -
 425 treating consciousness and quantum mechanics as aspects of the same underlying reality -
 426 points toward important new directions in physics.

427

428 **APPENDIX: MATHEMATICAL FRAMEWORK AND PREDICTIONS**

429 While this paper's primary contribution is conceptual, computational modeling suggests several
 430 preliminary mathematical relationships that may prove useful for theoretical physicists
 431 developing formal expressions of these ideas. The following formalism is offered not as
 432 definitive, but as a starting point for the mathematical investigation of this framework's
 433 implications.

- 434 1. **Modified Quantum State Description:** The conventional wave function becomes a
 435 function of both potential (P) and experiential (E) fields:

436

$$\psi(t) = f(P,E)$$

438

439 where the interaction between P and E accounts for:

- 440 • The accumulated history of measurements
- 441 • The temporal relationship between measurements
- 442 • The observer-system interaction

443

444 2. **Experience Operator:** To capture measurement history influence, we introduce an
445 experience operator $\hat{E}$:

446

$$\hat{E} = \sum_i \alpha_i M_i(t_i)$$

448

449 where M_i represents individual measurements at times t_i , and α_i are weighting factors
450 dependent on:

- 451 • Temporal distance from present measurement
- 452 • Measurement precision
- 453 • Inter-measurement coherence

454

455 3. **Modified Measurement Probability:** The probability of a particular measurement
456 outcome becomes:

457

$$P(m) = |\langle m | \hat{E} | P \rangle|^2$$

459

460 This modification to the Born rule incorporates the experiential field's influence through
461 $\hat{E}$, with weighting factors α_i creating interference patterns in sequential measurements.

462

463 4. **Modified Evolution Operator:** The complete evolution operator becomes:

464

$$U(t) = \exp(-iHt/\hbar) \cdot \exp(\hat{E}t)$$

466

467 where the second term represents the experiential field's influence.

468

469 5. **Predicted Correlations:** Sequential measurement correlations should follow:

470

$$R(\tau) = \langle M(t)M(t+\tau) \rangle \neq \langle M(t) \rangle \langle M(t+\tau) \rangle$$

472

473 with τ representing the time interval between measurements.

474

475 6. **Modified Probability Distribution:** The standard distribution becomes:

476

$$P'(x) = P(x)[1 + \gamma E(x)]$$

478

479 where γ represents the coupling strength between fields and $E(x)$ encodes measurement
480 history.

481

482

7. Key Predicted Effects

483

a) Memory Effects in Sequential Measurements: $P(x | x_{-1}, \dots, x_1) = |\psi(x)|^2 \cdot F(x, \{x_i\})$ where

484

$$F(x, \{x_i\}) = 1 + \beta \sum_i \exp(-|t-t_i|/\tau_c) \cdot g(|x-x_i|)$$

485

b) Temporal Resonance Effects: $R(\tau) = R_0[1 + \sum A \exp(-\tau/\tau) \cos(\omega\tau)]$

486

c) Observer-Dependent Coupling: $\gamma = \gamma_0(1 + \eta(O))$

487

d) Scale-Dependent Transition: $\gamma(N) = \gamma_0 \exp(-N/N_c)$

488

489 These relationships predict specific, measurable deviations from standard quantum mechanics,

490 particularly in:

491

- Sequential measurement patterns

492

- Temporal correlations

493

- Observer-dependent variations

494

- Scale-dependent transitions

495

496

497

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

498

This work represents independent research developed over thirteen years of dedicated

499

investigation into the foundations of physics and consciousness.

500

501

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

502

The author declares no competing interests.

503

504

REFERENCES

505

1. Aspect, A., Dalibard, J., & Roger, G. (1982). "Experimental Test of Bell's Inequalities Using Time-Varying Analyzers." *Physical Review Letters*, 49(25), 1804-1807.

506

507

2. Barad, K. (2007). *Meeting the Universe Halfway: Quantum Physics and the Entanglement of Matter and Meaning*. Duke University Press.

508

509

3. Barbour, J. (1999). *The End of Time: The Next Revolution in Physics*. Oxford University Press.

510

511

4. Bell, J. S. (1987). *Speakable and Unsayable in Quantum Mechanics*. Cambridge University Press.

512

513

5. Bohm, D. (1980). *Wholeness and the Implicate Order*. Routledge.

514

515

6. Bohr, N. (1935). "Can Quantum-Mechanical Description of Physical Reality Be Considered Complete?" *Physical Review*, 48, 696-702.

- 516 7. Carroll, S. (2019). *Something Deeply Hidden: Quantum Worlds and the Emergence of*
517 *Spacetime*. Dutton.
- 518 8. Conway, J., & Kochen, S. (2009). "The Strong Free Will Theorem." *Notices of the AMS*,
519 56(2), 226-232.
- 520 9. d'Espagnat, B. (2006). *On Physics and Philosophy*. Princeton University Press.
- 521 10. Davies, P. C. W. (1995). *About Time: Einstein's Unfinished Revolution*. Simon &
522 Schuster.
- 523 11. Deutsch, D. (2011). *The Beginning of Infinity: Explanations That Transform the World*.
524 Allen Lane.
- 525 12. Everett, H. (1957). "'Relative State' Formulation of Quantum Mechanics." *Reviews of*
526 *Modern Physics*, 29, 454-462.
- 527 13. Fuchs, C. A. (2017). "On Participatory Realism." In *Information and Interaction:*
528 *Eddington, Wheeler, and the Limits of Knowledge*, 113-134.
- 529 14. Ghirardi, G.C., Rimini, A., & Weber, T. (1986). "Unified dynamics for microscopic and
530 macroscopic systems." *Physical Review D*, 34, 470.
- 531 15. Giustina, M., et al. (2015). "Significant-Loophole-Free Test of Bell's Theorem with
532 Entangled Photons." *Physical Review Letters*, 115(25), 250401.
- 533 16. Hameroff, S., & Penrose, R. (2014). "Consciousness in the universe: A review of the
534 'Orch OR' theory." *Physics of Life Reviews*, 11(1), 39-78.
- 535 17. Hardy, L. (2013). "Quantum theory from five reasonable axioms." arXiv:quant-
536 ph/0101012v4.
- 537 18. Haroche, S. (2013). "Nobel Lecture: Controlling photons in a box and exploring the
538 quantum to classical boundary." *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 85(3), 1083.
- 539 19. Heisenberg, W. (1958). *Physics and Philosophy: The Revolution in Modern Science*.
540 Harper & Row.
- 541 20. Joos, E., et al. (2003). *Decoherence and the Appearance of a Classical World in*
542 *Quantum Theory*. Springer.
- 543 21. Kastner, R. E. (2013). *The Transactional Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics: The*
544 *Reality of Possibility*. Cambridge University Press.
- 545 22. Leggett, A. J. (2002). "Testing the limits of quantum mechanics: motivation, state of play,
546 prospects." *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter*, 14(15), R415.
- 547 23. Mermin, N. D. (2019). "Making Better Sense of Quantum Mechanics." *Reports on*
548 *Progress in Physics*, 82(1).
- 549 24. Omnès, R. (1994). *The Interpretation of Quantum Mechanics*. Princeton University
550 Press.
- 551 25. Penrose, R. (1994). *Shadows of the Mind: A Search for the Missing Science of*
552 *Consciousness*. Oxford University Press.
- 553 26. Price, H. (1996). *Time's Arrow and Archimedes' Point: New Directions for the Physics of*
554 *Time*. Oxford University Press.
- 555 27. Rovelli, C. (2018). *The Order of Time*. Riverhead Books.
- 556 28. Schlosshauer, M. (2007). *Decoherence and the Quantum-to-Classical Transition*.
557 Springer.
- 558 29. Stapp, H. P. (2011). *Mindful Universe: Quantum Mechanics and the Participating*
559 *Observer*. Springer.

- 560 30. von Neumann, J. (1955). *Mathematical Foundations of Quantum Mechanics*. Princeton
561 University Press.
- 562 31. Wheeler, J. A., & Zurek, W. H. (1983). *Quantum Theory and Measurement*. Princeton
563 University Press.
- 564 32. Wigner, E. P. (1967). "Remarks on the mind-body question." In *Symmetries and*
565 *Reflections*, Indiana University Press.
- 566 33. Zurek, W. H. (2003). "Decoherence, einselection, and the quantum origins of the
567 classical." *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 75(3), 715.